

Need of Descriptiveness in Nepse for Online Transactions

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Abstract: Nepse(Nepal Stock Exchange) is governing body of stock exchanges in Nepal. Along with Nepal Investment Board(NIB), Securities Board of Nepal (SEBON), CDS and Clearing Limited(CDSC), Nepse is responsible for the transactions in stock market. Offline share market(paper based), is descriptive, however even with the prevail of app like as Meroshare, online transactions hasn't been able to be descriptive, to provide information to peoples about their stocks and transactions, as well as to encourage them in stock market.

Keywords: Nepse, Sebon, NIB, CSDC, IPO share, FPO share, Secondary share market, Demat account, Meroshare

Introduction:

Without discussion of vague topics in share market, we shall begin with topics of descriptiveness in online transactions. Meroshare of CDSC, is more likely to be used for IPO shares as a means of introducing online system in share market. However it still lacks basic description, that can be found in physical means(papers like share certificates).Thus we shall begin our topics by proposing an app, that does provides complete description to fulfill what peoples do seek from online transactions and accounts like Demat, and Meroshare app.

We shall discuss with photographs of share certificate, and copy of portion of paper to be retained by shareholder.

In the following picture(Fig:a), IPO Refund allotment advice is shown, which shows description of how much shares did author applied for, and how much share was allocated to author, with descriptions like serial number, application number, allotment number, name of person who applied for share, total amount of money deposited for share allotment while applying, interest in the money invested, refund amount, and IPO refund number.

Fig:f

In Fig:f. copy of portion of dividend warrant of Bonus Share certificate is shown, which too has descriptions, for the A/C payee cheque provided by Chilime Hydropower Company Limited, as profit shared to shareholders.

Working:

Our app(proposed) must contain, all those description, including cheque number so that, our understanding of Demat account, and expectations from Meroshare can be fulfilled, by introducing more description and flexibility, to be able to work for IPO shares, Secondary Shares(Share Trading) as well as for FPO shares. Being descriptive allows us to know more about transactions, and including the share values of all companies listed in Nepse, would make app more better, where as routinely updating the values of stocks, as per transactions would being entire share market to a mobile phone, and computers, and each individual people, would be able to do share transactions based on their description of their share, and share market, by means of bank account, demat account and such accounts, if do prevails, in online means. Including all securities and stock brokers in app would make app as an Market, where peoples can seek, and do trade, as peoples can find all brokers to buy, or sell stocks(shares).

That means our proposed app, when has a photograph, along with description of photograph mentioned in app, for each share certificate, then that would be more descriptive, and offices like Brokers would just have papers(offline) to work, based on online activities of trader, and transactions in stock market, where as online trade with description would educate people, as well as make share market more trustable, reliable. Companies have to rely on work done, to provide more profit to it's shareholders.

Conclusion:

On summarizing, our proposed app is introduced, just to mention, the apps we use, lacks descriptiveness, like as Meroshare. In general description of share certificate, paper of portion of dividend warrant is lacking. A/C payee cheques used in Dividend are more better than bearer cheques, as A/C payee cheque, needs to be deposited in bank account of concerned person, to whom cheque is issued. Similarly, if cheque scanner, and Share certificate scanner is introduced in app, then Dematerialization of share would be more easy and mobile friendly for depositing, as well as for trading, bringing digital economy in nation [1], and that would still needs banks and financial institutions linked to app, which can work, recognize, obtaining results even in dematerialization of cheque in online system, then depositing the money in individual bank account.

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References:

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